

E-Learning Management System

Vaishnavi Metange¹, Pratiksha Gawande², Yashashri Ingle³, Kalyani Gawande⁴
^{1,2,3,4}Computer Science and Engineering, Sidhivinayak Technical Campus Shegaon, Maharashtra, India

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ABSTRACT

iSchool (E-Learning Management System) is a project which aims in developing an online application to provide Online Education, maintain Study Materials, keep Student records and collect Payments. This project has login features, Educator as Admin and Student as an user can login into their own portal separately. The Admin can login, through which the admin can monitor the whole system. This System can be used to search for course, add new courses, edit course, check payment status etc. The Admin after logging into his account can generate reports such as sell Report. The User can login into his account to follow course he purchased and can share his/her feedback.

Overall this project of ours is being developed to help the Educator (Admin) as well as Students (User) to provide Teaching-Learning platform in the best way possible.

Keywords: - Educator

1. INTRODUCTION

It is difficult to find time for the training necessary to gain new skills and boost your productivity. With **iSchool** you're able to learn at a pace that is comfortable for you. **iSchool** is a powerful Learning Management System implementing the latest trends in e-learning. E-Learning is learning utilizing electronic technologies to access educational curriculum outside of a traditional classroom. In most cases, it refers to a course, or program delivered completely online. We define eLearning as courses that are specifically delivered via the internet to somewhere other than the classroom where the professor is teaching. E-Learning has been proven to be a successful method of training and education is becoming a way of life for many citizens in India and across the World. **iSchool** Publisher is a professional team development environment for the rapid development of e-courses by their own.

Any Person who wants to gain new skills can join **iSchool**. A Person/Student/Learner has to fill up registration form which is absolutely Free. Once Learner registers successfully, they will get UserID/Email and Password for login into Student/Learner Panel. After login they can buy any course as per their choice or requirement which is available in **iSchool**. They can watch purchased video courses online and can submit their feedback. As well they can update their profile and can change password. Admin of this system will upload new courses which will be available for everyone. Admin can delete or edit student/learner details. Admin can modify course details and can check sells report.

1.1 Objective:

A flexible web-based learning experience allows you to go through a guided curriculum or choose lessons on an as-needed basis. Following are the main objectives:-

- Ability to recall previously learned material – Students/learners can watch video courses as many times as they need. If they forgot something during the course they can come back and watch that specific part anytime.
- Creative way to present lesson – It is very creative way to present lectures. It will surely enhance teaching ability of tutor.
- Low Cost – As nobody needs to travel or rent anything so it's very cost efficient.
- High Quality – As tutor do not has time boundation so he can teach in his own comfort time.
- Learn anytime from anywhere – Students/Learners can start learning anytime from anywhere they just required internet connection with a compatible device.
- Improve course quality according to learner's feedback – Tutor can improve their course as per student's feedback. It will help tutor to improve their ability to teach.
- Earn Money Online – As courses are paid so we can say it's an online teaching business which has no boundaries means students/learners can join from across the world so this system can make good business with good quality.

2. METHODOLOGY

The Following Data Flow diagram depicts activities to perform while using E learning management system

2.1 Data Flow Diagram (DFD)

Data flow diagram is graphical representation of flow of data in an information system. It uses defined symbols like rectangles, circles and arrows, plus short text labels, to show data inputs, outputs, storage points and the routes between each destination. Data flowcharts can range from simple, even hand-drawn process overviews, to in-depth, multi-level DFDs that dig progressively deeper into how the data is handled.

2.1.1 DFD 0 Level

The 0 Level DFD shows flow of data of application. DFD Level 0 is also called a Context Diagram. It's a basic overview of the whole system or process being analyzed or modeled.

Fig 1:O Level DFD

2.1.2 DFD 1 Level

DFD Level 1 provides a more detailed breakout of pieces of the Context Level Diagram. This DFD describes main functions carried out by the system, as we break down the high-level process of the Context Diagram into its sub-processes.

Fig 2:Level 1:DFD

3. SYSTEM DESIGN

The systems design approach first appeared right before World War II, when engineers were trying to solve complex control and communications problems. They needed to be able to standardize their work into a formal discipline with proper methods, especially for new fields like information theory, operations research and computer science in general. System design is the process of defining the elements of a system such as the architecture, modules and components, the different interfaces of those components and the data that goes through that system. It is meant to satisfy specific needs and requirements of a business or organization through the engineering of a coherent and well-running system.

3.1 Input Module

In order to complete the tasks of iSchooland to get output by using this application work, there is need of some input based on the work that is to be carried out by using it. Different kinds of input are required for different purposes.

- Student/Learner Registration
- Course
- Lesson
- Feedback
- Payment Status

3.2 Output Module

The project named “iSchool E-Learning Management System” is being made keeping in mind to solve the activities that are carried out in the Education. By using this,Admin can easily do many things like as:

- Student/Learner List
- Course Detail
- Lesson Detail
- Sell Report
- Payment Receipt

3.3 Modularization Detail

Without Registration

- Home – This module contains all the links of the application such as Courses, Payment Status, Login, Sign Up, Feedback Section and Contact.
- Courses – This module contains list of all the courses which are available at iSchool.
- Payment Status – This module is used to check Payment status after purchasing a course.
- Login – This module is used to login into Student/Learner Panel.
- Sign Up – This module is used to register for the Student/Learner Panel.
- Feedback – This section shows feedback given by registered students/learners.
- Contact – Learner can use this section to contact the admin/tutor for any kind of queries.

Student Panel

- Profile – This module contains all the details about Student/Learner as well as Student can update their details.
- My Courses – This module contains list of all purchased courses.
- Feedback – This module is used to write feedback.
- Change Password – Students can use this module to change password.
- Logout – This module is used to return back to Home Page.

Admin Panel

- Dashboard – This module displays overview of whole application.
- Courses – This module contains all the courses.
- Lessons – This module contains all the lesson depends on course id.
- Students – This module displays all the registered student details.
- Sell Report – This module is used to view and print sells report.
- Payment Status – This module displays payment status in more details.
- Feedback – This module displays feedback given by students.
- Change Password – Admin can use this module to change password.
- Logout – This module is used to return back to Home Page.

3.4 Process Logic Home:

When the user click on this tab, it will display the other modules and pages of the website such as courses, payment status, login, sign up, popular section, feedback section, contact and admin login. This module will be used to display the brief introduction of the project and will show the title of the project.

Courses:

Student can view all available courses by clicking on courses tab where he can choose course according to his own interest and by clicking on a particular course, will display more details with lesson title of the course, if he wants to purchase he will be able to make payment (required login).

Payment Status:

After purchasing course student will be provided an order id which can be used to get the status of payment using Payment status tab. If student wants he can get print out of his payment status.

Login:

This is a login form. Student/Learner can use their own email and password to login into the student panel.

Sign Up:

This is a Registration form for new Students/Learners. New Students/Learners can fill up the form for registration and after successful registration they can use their email id and password to login into the application.

Feedback:

This is very simple section which displays feedback given by the registered student.

Contact:

Learner can use this section to contact the admin/tutor for any kind of queries.

Student Panel:- Profile:

Students/Learners can view their student id, registered email id, name, occupation, profile picture as well as they can modify and update the new data if they need.

My Courses:

Students can view all courses which they purchased. This is the place where they can start watching lectures by clicking on Watch Course button which leads to course playlist where they can watch the entire lesson of course.

Feedback:

Students can view/write feedback.

Change Password:

Students can use this module to change password.

Logout:

This module is used exit student panel and return back to Home Page.

Admin Panel

Dashboard:

This module displays overview of whole application such as number of course, number of registered students etc.

Courses:

This is the most important module of admin panel where Admin can view list of course as well as add new courses and modify or delete courses.

Lessons:

Admin can view lesson based on course id as well as new lesson can be added to the course and modification or deletion is also possible using this module.

Students:

Admin can view registered students details. Admin can add, edit and delete student.

Feedback:

Admin can view/delete feedback given by student.

Sell Report:

Analyzing sales is very important for any kind of business and this module is perfect for analyzing sales based on date.

It will generate sells report which can be possible to print out for office records.

Payment Status:

If student file any complaints regarding payment Admin can use this module to display payment status in more details such as bank name, transaction id, payment date etc.

Change Password:

Admin can use change password.

Logout:

This module is used exit admin panel and return back to Home Page.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The iSchool E-Learning Maintenance Management System has been computed successfully and was also tested successfully by taking "Test Cases". It is user friendly, and has required options, which can be utilized by the user to perform the desired operations.

The Software is developed using HTML, CSS, JS as front end and PHP, MySQL as back end in windows environment.

The goals that are achieved by the software are:

- Simplification of the operations
- Less processing time and getting required information
- User friendly
- Portable and flexible for further enhancement

5. FUTURE SCOPE

- More than one tutor can be added
- Interaction between Student and Tutor can be improved by introducing Discussion forum
- Quiz Facility may enhance this application's market value
- Live Class can be added

6. REFERENCES

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